

Record of living individual of the freshwater snail *Gyraulus rossmaessleri* (Auerswald, 1852) in Slovakia after thirty-eight years (Gastropoda: Planorbidae)

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A living adult and two fresh shells of the freshwater snail *Gyraulus rossmaessleri* (Auerswald, 1852) (Gastropoda, Planorbidae) were found in the lower Morava River alluvial plain in SW Slovakia after thirty-eight years.

The shell of *Gyraulus rossmaessleri* is small- to medium sized, usually not exceeding 4 mm in diameter and 1.3 mm in height. It is similar to *Gyraulus laevis* (Alder, 1838) in shape, but umbilicus and sutures are shallower; the whorls are rounded, never angled or keeled. The aperture has a characteristic thickened lip (that does not necessarily terminate growth). Growth marks indicating growth interruptions are regularly present (desiccation of habitat). The surface is not smooth, but rather dull, with a very fine reticulate sculpture (spiral striae very close to each other). The colour is reddish brown (MEIER-BROOK 1983).

Locality and material examined: SW Slovakia, 4 km W from village of Závod (48°32'47" N, 16°57'52" E) (grid reference databank of Fauna of Slovakia DFS – 7468c), temporary pool in forest fragment of the non-inundated area behind the dam, gravel-sandy bottom covered with mud and thick layer of poplar and ash leaves (Fig. 1), 149.0 m a.s.l., 8 October, 2001, E. Bulánková and J. Halgoš leg., one living adult and two fresh shells found. The material was not dissected, identified only by shell morphology. T. Čejka det. et coll., M. Horsák rev.

Distribution: *Gyraulus rossmaessleri* is an European species with very restricted central European range. Its

more or less continuous occurrence is known from S, W, central and eastern Europe: Germany (MEIER-BROOK 1983; GLÖER 2002), Austria (FALKNER 1995), Czech Republic (JUŘIČKOVÁ et al. 2001), Slovakia (LUČIVJANSKÁ & ŠTEFFEK 1991), Switzerland (TURNER et al. 1998), Poland (PIECHOCKI 1979), Hungary (RICHNOVSZKY & PINTÉR 1979); according to SCHLESCH (1942) in Lithuania as well.

LISICKÝ (1991) did not mention the species in the monograph of Slovak molluscs; few records were discovered by LUČIVJANSKÁ & ŠTEFFEK (1991) in collection of T. Weisz from 1960s (the latest record came from 1963, village of Senné, East Slovakia). ČEJKA (2000) found 3 fresh empty shells in the flood debris of the Danube River in the Bratislava City.

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Fig. 1. The habitat of the freshwater snail *Gyraulus rossmaessleri* in the dried-up stage (SW Slovakia, the lower Morava River)